

Future of Space Operations

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Abstract

This article explores the future of the Air Force's space applications and operations, based on the performance of new defence systems and innovative technologies, updating current doctrines and Concepts of Operations (CONOPS). It explains how robust space capabilities are an indispensable foundation for modern air power, analyzing ways they support find, fix, track, target, engage, and neutralize defensive systems (ground – sea – air – space). It predicts future supremacy of our air power and dominance in the aerospace area, focusing on early perception of development, staff training preparation, and timely acquisition of suitable air & space systems, technologies, & infrastructures.

Keywords

Future space applications, Technology's role, Space capabilities' importance, Predictions for Air power supremacy, anti-satellite, Direct Energy Weapons, Space Security, emerging disruptive technologies.

1. Introduction

As we envision air and space threats by 2040, achieving technological supremacy through defence innovation is essential for Air Power dominance and airspace security. This need anchors the European Defence Agency's (EDA) Capabilities Development Plan (CDP), where the long-term assessment identifies global space threats—such as operational anti-satellite (ASAT) systems and emerging technologies like parasitic satellites—as key strategic factors, alongside capability requirements and technological opportunities. The CDP's Long-Term Capability Assessment of modern Air Power explores trends and standard military tasks over a 20+ year timeline to counter these risks.¹

The aim is to equip EU member states' Air Forces with insights into factors influencing National Air-Space Power from 2040 onward.² National Space Power—the capacity to control and exploit outer space for defence and national goals—underpins security, independence, and societal well-being.¹ As space becomes a contested domain for mankind, this capability is crucial to safeguard citizens against escalating threats to satellite infrastructure.

This article provides a summary of the factors that will be taken into consideration in future Space Operations. It also offers valuable insight into the CDP, while also identifying strategic challenges which are likely to shape the operational environment for the Air Force beyond 2040.

Additionally, it is useful for the reader to understand today's military space applications and operations, to have a better view of the future technological efforts and achievements in space.³

Today's Space Ops include significant activities conducted by military forces against satellites in orbit for many operational needs. Satellites nowadays face physical and electronic threats. Physical threats encompass satellite destruction by ground-to-space or air-to-space missiles, satellite destruction by incident after collision with space debris, and satellite destruction or temporary neutralisation by High Altitude Nuclear Explosion (HANE) or by Direct Energy Weapons, such as lasers.⁴ Electronic threats

¹ **Operations:** All the military actions taken place in the aerospace (Defensive & Offensive) plus all the activities held in space (military & nonmilitary) supporting military means & OPS centers.

National Space Power: The degree of use & utilization of aerospace area and aerospace technology by the state and its agencies. It determines its general power against the rest of the states - neighbors -, acting as a force multiplier in the overall National Power of the country. This is obtained by analyzing the term "Degree of Use - utilization of space" (Du) by a state in the equation of its total National Power (P_N).

$$P_N = P_M \times P_P \times P_O \times P_C \times P_T.$$

Where: P_M = Military power, P_P = Political power, P_O = Economical power, P_C = Coalitions' Power,

$P_T = (P_U \times D_U)$ = Power of technology (Is the product of the universal technology P_U by the State degree of technology use P_U . See J. Epstein, Measuring Military Power. Princeton, NJ, USA: Princeton Univ. Press, 1989.

include Satcom interception by airborne EW,⁵ interception by ground-based EW, uplink and downlink interception, uplink and downlink jamming, and geolocation.⁶

GPS Jammer 8 watt with omni directional antenna

This is a map of GPS interference in and around Israel. If you are sailing around that area be prepared for GPS and AIS issues

During Israeli air operations against Hezbollah and Hamas in 2024, an old threat has re-emerged: Anti-Satellite Weapons, commonly known as ASAT. ASAT weapons, increasingly deployed as microsattellites equipped with various payloads, represent a significant challenge. These high-tech multi-delivery systems are designed to incapacitate or destroy satellites for strategic or tactical purposes, threatening the supremacy of air and space power.⁷

China has an operational ASAT system and is quietly developing more advanced capabilities; a parasitic satellite is presented as a key component of China’s asymmetric combat strategy.⁸ No one can predict future air or space threats and conflicts with certainty, but we must maintain the necessary capabilities to respond effectively.

2. Future Military Trends Assessment

Since 2004, the European Defence Agency (EDA) has been actively involved in space-related activities.⁹ To support the long-term assessment of Air Force capability and space operations, the EDA has launched an evaluation process aligned with the CDP’s short, mid, and long-term periods, targeting 2040 and beyond. This process includes two key activities: analyzing the future operational context and outlining hypothetical operational scenarios.

2.1 Future operational context

An analysis of the future operational context, considering worldwide geopolitical and socio-economic macro trends, including possible security and environmental challenges is based on a comprehensive review and assessment of official publications and documents, from the European Union (EU), Member States (MS), and NATO relevant entities. These documents refer to strategic and technological foresight in the long term and the identification of specific strategic factor trends in 2040 and beyond.

Climate change could become a potential driver for all remaining trends since the consequences may be exploited intentionally producing significant security challenges. The social structure is likely to undergo significant changes due to demographic issues. New technologies, alongside

greater dependence on key components, will also have major impacts on employment, required skills, and economic opportunities. The growing interdependence of resources between Western and Eastern states is altering the global balance of power, increasingly tilting towards Asia and giving rise to a multipolar international order with heightened competition.

Social media, propaganda, social engineering, and information control are expected to be the primary drivers of social destabilisation, which may be used to disseminate misinformation, foster social polarisation, instil distrust, and encourage brain-drain among the population. Finally, technology becomes particularly relevant in the grey zone, driving activities such as political and election interference, cyber threats and attacks, economic coercion, the use of proxies, and numerous other measures — including military action.

2.2 Changes in the military character of war

Technological superiority is expected to be a major factor in future warfare.¹⁰ The evolution of current technologies and the disruptive nature of new ones will allow significant enhancement of military capabilities but will also pose several challenges for EU armed forces. The expected challenge for future technological developments is to reach a nearly real-time situational awareness. The capability to operate in any domain simultaneously is subject to maintaining robust cognitive ability and resilience over the adversary, since all actions in traditional domains have effects in the cognitive dimension.

Technological advances in big data analysis and artificial intelligence-driven systems will improve the assessment of the multi-domain operational environment and determine how to take and keep the initiative in the ‘Battle of the Narrative’. In addition, expected developments in quantum and blockchain technologies should be considered as enablers to create more robust and resilient communication systems. An enhanced cyberspace situational awareness will be necessary to ensure continuity and early detection of cyber vulnerabilities.

2.3 New materials

Technological advances are already occurring at an ever-faster pace. This accelerates the race for technological superiority in many fields such as digitalisation, biotechnologies and human enhancement, data management, space technologies, hypersonic weapons, artificial intelligence, new materials, nanotechnologies, manufacturing processes, and quantum technologies.

2.4 Biotechnologies and human enhancement

In the military field, technologies such as human enhancement and new materials will significantly improve the survivability and effectiveness of units and platforms, while the development of novel disruptive weapons (such as hypersonic and directed energy weapons) will bring new opportunities and challenges to the battlefield.

2.5 Quantum technologies

Accessibility and democratisation of technology are expected to significantly reduce the technology gap between states and non-state actors, leading military forces, and state actors to lose their exclusivity of access to high-end technology and weapons. Non-state actors and even individuals will have greater access to advanced armaments and technology, which will open new possibilities for hybrid warfare tactics and increase the risks of confrontations, even long-lasting in the grey zone.

3. Future Capability Trends

Identification of long-term capability trends and associated challenges with technological leaps has been driven by the need to keep future military advantage. It will be necessary to agree on standardisation policies across armed forces and nations for these trends to materialize.

3.1 Fight for Cognitive Superiority

Extensive use of digital technology and increasing uncertainty in society have intensified competition for cognitive superiority and the perception of reality.¹¹ Future technological developments aim for nearly real-time situation awareness, requiring robust cognitive ability and resilience over the adversary. Enhanced cyberspace situational awareness is necessary for early detection of cyber vulnerabilities.

3.2 Multi Domain Connectivity “By Design”

The operational environment is volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous, accentuated by new technologies, globalisation, digitalisation, and pervasive connectivity.¹² This implies employing forces of different sizes and capabilities, from large-scale manoeuvres to special operations, possibly unmanned. Technological developments in digitalisation, communication, sensors, and data analysis require an enhanced multi-domain operational picture for real-time situational awareness, with decentralised command and control systems to support decision-makers.

3.3 Pervasiveness of Multilayer Maneuverable Engagement

Strong development of long-range, precision weapons and swarming threats demands integrated air and missile defence systems with robust attrition capacity. Emerging technologies make it necessary to enhance integration of air and missile defence systems.¹³ Ballistic missiles, hypersonic weapons, and drone swarms are difficult to counter, requiring early warning, advanced sensors, and integrated networks. Hypersonic technology expands air power attributes (speed, range, flexibility, accuracy), challenging detection, tracking, and engagement with reduced decision time.

3.4 Electromagnetic Spectrum Dominance

Increased use of the electromagnetic spectrum by military forces offers opportunities for electronic warfare. Electromagnetic spectrum operations (EMSO) enable planning and execution of military operations in all domains, increasing in importance in a digitised, connected world. Electromagnetic spectrum dominance is crucial for superiority, requiring robust infrastructure to confront disruptive threats.

3.5 Heterogeneous Energy Availability for Operational Environments

Future battlefield digitalisation presents a higher, heterogeneous energy demand to generate, store, transport, and distribute energy efficiently. New weapon systems imply high energy demand at specific moments, while bases need to be efficient and self-sustainable, considering climate change and resource shortages. Technologies supporting energy generation, storage, and distribution are essential.

3.6 Extensive Space Capabilities: from Enabling to Shaping the Future Battlefield

Reliance on space capabilities rises as warfare changes, with smaller, cheaper satellites making space a contested domain. Space assets shape operational deployment across domains, enabling beyond line-of-sight communications, real-time surveillance, precision weapons, and command and control. Future operations depend on space for cognitive superiority and communication, requiring robust, resilient assets and related doctrine to shape military operations.

3.7 Coexistence of Analogue and Digital Defence Mindsets

By 2040, a digitised, technology-dependent world will shift generations' mindsets, affecting armed forces with a transition period to accommodate different abilities. Legacy equipment coexists with analogue and digital approaches. Exploiting technological development requires evolution from an 'analogue' to a 'digital' mindset, alongside advances in biotechnology, nanotechnology, and machine learning.

4. Technology Impact On Future Military Capabilities

Emerging disruptive technologies (EDTs), from a capability development perspective, will influence new military applications and challenges within the future battlespace.

4.1 Internet of Things

The Internet of Things utilises numerous sensors for real-time information collection and analysis, enabling persistent monitoring of systems and environments. This facilitates remote supervision and informed decision-making. Extensive sensor networks across domains and

platforms provide a decentralised operational view, supporting decision-making with valuable data. For air defence, these networks deliver real-time information to detect and counter airborne threats like autonomous systems, swarming threats, or hypersonic missiles with distinct attack vectors.

4.2 Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence-based systems offer multiple military applications, increasingly supporting decision-making processes. Robust verification and validation ensure algorithmic effectiveness. Autonomy in engagement chains raises ethical and legal concerns, necessitating clear rules and human oversight definitions (e.g., in the loop vs. on the loop). In cyberspace, artificial intelligence analyses data to identify weaknesses for offensive and defensive actions. Strategically, it impacts deterrence by detecting strategic weapons, potentially altering geopolitical and nuclear postures.¹⁴

4.3 Biotechnology & Human Enhancement

Biotechnologies and human enhancement enable real-time monitoring of combatants' health, mood, and status, enhancing situational awareness. Sensors in clothing or equipment monitor parameters and recommend actions, while micro-sensors and augmented reality improve mission control. Unmanned systems integration with human capabilities supports human-machine collaboration, though invasive brain-computer connections remain unfeasible short-term.

4.4 Robotics & Autonomous Systems

Autonomous systems are rapidly integrated into military capabilities, enhancing information acquisition, surveillance, intelligence, and routine tasks such as border surveillance with minimal supervision. These systems improve combat capability, unconstrained by human limitations, thus reducing combatant risk. They optimise transport of cargo and personnel, supporting 'on-demand' logistics through manned-autonomous combinations. This impacts maintenance, repair, and medical support by automating tasks and reducing specialist deployment. In combat and in-field hospitals, autonomy enables faster healthcare tasks, lessening the need for specialist doctors to be physically present. Additionally, autonomous systems can be utilized in electronic warfare to protect military assets by detecting and neutralizing threats in the electromagnetic spectrum and performing offensive actions like signal jamming.

Israeli C-130J: Supplies dropping in front line of Gaza ops with auto remote parachutes.

4.5 Advanced Materials & Manufacturing

Advances in materials and manufacturing techniques influence military capabilities across metals, production, synthetic biology, nanotechnology, and stealth designs. Metamaterial-based communication systems enhance electromagnetic spectrum use, while antennas improve power, directionality, and frequency range for electronic warfare. Metamaterials also boost optical and infrared sensor performance for detection and identification.

4.6. Hypersonic Weapon Systems

Hypersonic weapons present a significant challenge due to their distinct behaviour compared with traditional armament and munitions.¹⁵ Their advanced performances in speed, manoeuvrability, and trajectory necessitate new detection systems and countermeasures, altering current air and missile defence concepts and architectures. These weapons can strike long-range targets quickly and accurately, evading detection systems, thus limiting adversaries' reaction time and countering anti-access capabilities. The potential incorporation of nuclear capabilities by some actors may shift strategic deterrence, destabilizing the strategic environment by rethinking nuclear strategies. Consequently, more sophisticated defence systems are required at tactical and strategic levels. Given the short response times, early warning and detection are critical enablers for effective countermeasures. This demands extensive sensor networks for launch-phase detection, with interconnectivity and interoperability across domains. Non-kinetic effectors, such as electronic warfare systems, directed energy weapons, or electromagnetic pulses, offer solutions, particularly against saturation attacks, while cooperation is essential for deploying capabilities with the necessary geographic coverage and rapid response.

Conventional payloads

Enhanced payloads

4.7 New Space Technologies

Reduced costs and technological gaps drive space service growth among state, non-state, and commercial actors. Space supports military operations with communications, observation, and sensing, improving planning and execution. Increased use heightens competition and threats like engagement-capable assets and debris, requiring protection measures.

Communications and Positioning, Navigation, and Timing (PNT)

Space as a conflict domain

ISTAR - Intelligence & counterintelligence

4.8. Quantum Technologies

Quantum technology harnesses quantum physics principles in applications, impacting fields like computing, sensors, and communications by enhancing data collection, processing, encryption, and transmission. It may be utilised for cyberspace defensive and offensive operations, enabling new attack vectors and improving traditional hacking methods' effectiveness. Quantum technologies will strengthen information transmission and communications security, facilitating secure connections and interoperability among battlefield systems—drones, aircraft, ships, soldiers, and command and control. Combining artificial intelligence with quantum technologies will provide advanced decision support tools for command and control.

Cybersecurity

Improved PNT Capabilities

Electronic warfare

Human augmentation, medical devices and bio-sensing

Quantum underwater warfare

Fast and secure communications

Force protection

Increased situational awareness

4.9 Blockchain

Blockchain enables information to be recorded securely and distributed, creating immutable digital records for transactions, communications, and supply chains, ensuring privacy and data integrity. Its use in command and control guarantees information authenticity and proper order transmission, enhancing accurate, agile, and automated execution. In cyber defence, it adds a security layer, enabling real-time data authentication and validation, complicating manipulation or detection by adversaries. Additionally, it enhances logistics and supply chain efficiency and security by providing visibility of the supplier network, guaranteeing parts' origin, and facilitating traceability.

**Robust and enduring C2
and intelligence**

**More secure and reliable
supply chain**

5. Future Requirements For Military Capabilities

5.1 Command Capabilities

Command capabilities are primarily shaped by technologies tied to information management and communications. Technologies like the Internet of Things, machine learning, and blockchain will be vital in this area, where cyber capabilities serve both defensive and offensive roles. Future communications will support effective interagency coordination, relying on an integrated network to counter misinformation campaigns. Big data and data processing will aid in assessing information and forming a robust, cooperative combat cloud.

Future armed forces require cyber-resilient networks providing integrated, continuous command and control (C2) applications, data services, and communication for multi-domain operations. Command and control systems must adopt a distributed approach, resilience against electronic warfare and cyber threats, and adaptability to emerging doctrines. The congested environment will be influenced by technological developments in EDTs, including new space technologies, autonomous systems, robotics, human enhancement, quantum, and blockchain. Space domain redundancy will enhance communications for improved interagency coordination.

5.2 Information Capabilities

Information and cognitive superiority will be a critical aspect of the future operational environment, marked by an ultra-digitised, connected society with vast information to share. The ability to collect, process, analyse, and transmit this data securely and promptly is vital for military intelligence.¹⁶ Key technologies driving future information capabilities include those related to communications, connectivity, big data management, analysis, and digitisation. In the forthcoming battle for information, space and cyberspace domains will be primary sources of situational awareness for armed forces. Cyberspace will serve as the main channel for storing and transmitting military data, alongside hosting society's digital media information, increasingly significant for cognitive warfare. Other technological developments, such as unmanned systems, autonomous systems, advanced sensors, Internet of Things devices, artificial intelligence, and blockchain, will offer new opportunities for intelligence gathering, transmissions, and data analysis.¹⁷

5.3 Engagements Capabilities

Engagement capabilities will be enhanced through the development of a new generation of weapons and platforms, significantly altering confrontations. The growing use of hybrid warfare tactics, information warfare, and psychological operations will play a vital role on the battlefield. Technologies such as new materials, advanced sensors, and artificial intelligence will enable smart munitions with greater precision, power, and range. This weaponry is expected to facilitate faster engagement over longer distances with reduced risk of collateral damage. Advances in energy production and storage will support directed energy weapons (DEW) with improved range and power, broadening their application across domains. These weapons, both lethal and non-lethal, will effectively counter emerging threats like drone swarms or hypersonic missiles. Electronic warfare and cyber offensive means will be crucial in dominating the congested electromagnetic spectrum of future battlefields, essential for achieving military superiority.¹⁸

5.4 Protect Capabilities

Future operational environment challenges and threats will necessitate significant enhancements in force protection for personnel, vehicles, infrastructures, facilities, and military assets. Novel materials will improve physical protection, including vehicles' armour, personal equipment, and infrastructures. Equipment, platforms, facilities, personnel, and electronic systems must operate in increasingly extreme and rapidly changing environmental conditions. As the cyber domain will convey vast critical information for military operations, cybersecurity will be a cornerstone of future force protection. Cryptography and active cyber countermeasures will be vital to secure communications and prevent data interception. Artificial intelligence-enabled systems will automatically generate responses and reveal adversaries' deceptive behaviours, including through social engagements, news reactions, and reports to decision-makers. Advanced sensing means, such as quantum sensors, space assets, extensive detection networks, and miniaturised sensors, will detect threats with greater precision and at extended distances, crucial for identifying and engaging stealth platforms, small assets, and fast-moving threats across all domains.

5.5 Deploy Capabilities

Future deployment activities are expected to be significantly influenced by advancements in artificial intelligence, robotics, autonomous systems, human enhancement, and the digitised, interconnected world. Readiness and rapid deployment capabilities will be essential to address fast-shifting conflicts in an operational environment with heightened tempo. Individuals, equipment, infrastructure, logistics lines, and platforms must be primed for swift commanding, mobilising, and deployment, ensuring full operational status upon reaching the theatre. Utilising autonomous systems, space assets, surveillance networks, and civilian and commercial infrastructure will be vital for persistent monitoring of adversary movements and identifying threats. Interaction with civilian entities will also decrease reliance on military facilities. Moreover, employing modular, scalable multi-role platforms will be necessary to optimise vehicle tasks and reduce dependence on specific-purpose units.

5.6 Sustain Capabilities

The future operational environment will call for major improvements and changes in military sustainment capabilities. Future tactics and technology developments will change many aspects of sustainment tasks, though they will also bring several challenges to logistics and supply chains. Several technologies, such as robotics and unmanned systems, Internet of Things, and artificial intelligence, among others, will have major impacts on how sustainment tasks are planned and conducted. The wider use of robotics and autonomous systems in logistics will allow us to improve overall efficiency while reducing sustainment risks and personnel needs.

6. Space Communications

In an era where information dominance is crucial to national security, satellite communications (satcom) form a cornerstone of modern defence strategies. This section examines the technical aspects of satcom and highlights its strategic importance in national defence, providing a roadmap for utilizing these technologies to enhance military capabilities.

6.1 Technical Aspects of Satcom

Satcom's efficiency is further enhanced through advanced modulation, encryption, and orbit selection strategies. Spread spectrum and frequency hopping techniques mitigate risks of jamming and interception, crucial in maintaining operational security. Geostationary (GEO), Medium Earth Orbit (MEO), and Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites are chosen based on required communication latency and coverage area, optimizing the strategic use of these assets.

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6.2 Strategic Importance in National Defence

Satellite communications are fundamental to national defence for several reasons, each correlating with the unique capabilities that satcom systems offer, Enhanced Command and Control (C2) Capabilities, Robust Intelligence, Surveillance, and Reconnaissance (ISR), Precision Navigation and Timing (PNT), Interoperability in Coalition Operations, Rapid Deployment and Flexibility and Enhanced Cybersecurity and Resilience.

7. Conclusions

We have endeavoured to anticipate the air and space threats that may emerge over the long term, drawing on global macro trends. This assessment rests on identified strategic factor tendencies and technological foresight extending to 2040 and beyond.

We foresee a transformation in the military nature of warfare, propelled by anticipated technological superiority. Advances such as space technology enhancements, hypersonic weapons, near real-time situational awareness, an enhanced multi-domain operational picture, rapid big data analysis, more robust and resilient communication systems, improved cyberspace situational awareness, and accelerated handling of complex, data-intensive tasks

through innovative artificial intelligence applications will fundamentally bolster upgraded doctrines for air and space superiority and supremacy.

Hybrid warfare techniques, digital technologies enabling distribution and decentralization, automated command and control (C2) systems aiding decision-makers, the emerging "Combat Cloud" concept, and escalating swarming threats—supported by high-tech weapons and air and space platforms, both manned and unmanned—will define the evolving threat landscape. Electromagnetic spectrum operations will play a pivotal enabling role in the planning and execution of air-space operations across all domains. Consequently, space assets must be robust, reliable, resilient, and redundant to ensure sustained operational availability.

New materials, biotechnologies, human enhancements, and quantum technologies will revolutionize existing approaches to operational military tasks, encompassing command, control, communications, computers, and intelligence (C4I), engagement, force protection, and logistics.

Significant operational advantages will arise from rapid learning and the continuous enhancement of cognitive capacities. Multi-domain connectivity "by design" will adeptly address future offensive, defensive, and supporting military requirements on a global scale.

Technologies such as the Internet of Things, artificial intelligence, biotechnology and human enhancement, robotics and autonomous systems, and advanced materials and manufacturing will drive the creation of more effective, durable, and reliable military systems and equipment. New space, quantum, and blockchain technologies will deliver essential services critical to military air operations, particularly in cyberspace.

The space domain's footprint and redundancy will enhance communications, fostering superior interagency coordination among stakeholders. Space and cyberspace domains will serve as primary sources of situational awareness, with cyberspace acting as the principal conduit for storing and transmitting military-managed data and hosting society's digital media information, which will grow increasingly vital for cognitive warfare.

Engagement capabilities will be markedly improved through a new generation of weapons and platforms, fundamentally reshaping confrontations. Similarly, hybrid warfare tactics, information warfare, and psychological operations, amplified by artificial intelligence, will assume a progressively central role on the battlefield. For engagements, force protection, and deployment, leveraging autonomous systems, space assets, and surveillance networks alongside civilian and commercial infrastructures will prove indispensable in maintaining persistent oversight of adversary movements and pinpointing potential threats, thereby reinforcing operational dominance.

However, these projections for future military capabilities and operations, with a focus on space activities and technological developments, present a formidable challenge for the next generation of Air Force officers. Their understanding and active engagement are imperative to drive the transformative shift in air and space operations from the present to the future, guided by a clear and enduring doctrinal principle: *"Air Space Superiority & Supremacy Forever."* This vision demands their commitment to adapt, innovate, and lead, ensuring that air and space forces remain unrivalled in an increasingly contested global arena.

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